

Review

Qigong as a Complementary Intervention for Cognitive and Motor Decline in Alzheimer's and Parkinson's Disease: A Literature Review.

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Abstract

The global ageing population increases the incidence of neurodegenerative diseases, such as dementia and Parkinson's disease, with limited pharmacological treatments. Traditional Chinese Medicine, with practices like *Qigong*, offers promising complementary approaches. The objective of this work is to contextualise and analyse the scientific evidence on the effects of *Qigong* as a complementary intervention on cognitive and motor decline associated with neurodegenerative diseases, exploring the underlying mechanisms. For this purpose, a review of the scientific literature on the application of *Qigong* in the treatment of dementia and Parkinson's disease was conducted, focusing on clinical studies and mechanisms of action. *Qigong* shows positive effects in preventing mild cognitive decline and in improving cognitive functions, such as memory and visuospatial ability. It reduces inflammatory and oxidative stress markers, improves metabolic and cardiovascular health, and modulates brain activity. In Parkinson's disease, it stabilises motor performance, improves gait and sleep quality, and reduces inflammatory markers. Therefore, *Qigong* emerges as a promising intervention for cognitive and neurological health, with benefits ranging from the prevention of cognitive decline to the improvement of Parkinson's disease symptoms. The practice seems to modulate brain activity, produce biochemical effects, and improve motor function, contributing to increased quality of life. Additional studies are needed to explore different forms of *Qigong* and its application in various types of dementia.

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1. Introduction

The increase in life expectancy observed worldwide in recent decades has led to a significant growth in the elderly population. According to United Nations estimates ¹, the global population aged 60 or older is expected to reach 2.1 billion by 2050. This phenomenon of population ageing brings with it a growing challenge: the increased incidence of neurodegenerative diseases, with dementia standing out as the most prevalent condition.

Dementia is a syndrome used to describe a set of symptoms that affect the brain and its cognitive function, such as memory, language, reasoning, and judgment. It is not a specific disease, but rather a set of symptoms that can result from different diseases and conditions ^{2,3}. Among these conditions, Alzheimer's disease is the most common, accounting for more than 60% of cases ⁴⁻⁶.

Alzheimer's Disease is a chronic neurodegenerative disease that affects the central nervous system, leading to progressive cognitive decline. Its impact extends far beyond the affected individual, imposing a significant burden on public health ⁷, as well as considerable family and social costs, due to its slow progression and profound effect on quality of life ^{8,9}. Conventional pharmacological treatments, although available, have limitations in terms of efficacy ^{7,10,11}.

In turn, Parkinson's disease is the second most common progressive neurodegenerative disease ¹². It is characterised by the degeneration of dopaminergic neurons, which triggers a series of changes that affect movement, mental health, sleep, pain perception, and other aspects of health. The most common symptoms include tremors, painful muscle contractions, speech difficulties, and changes in the senses of smell and taste ^{13,14}. The available treatments are limited and have side effects and reduced efficacy in many cases ¹⁵⁻¹⁷. This reality highlights the importance of exploring complementary therapeutic approaches, with the aim of improving the quality of life of patients with Alzheimer's and Parkinson's Disease and providing more comprehensive care ¹⁸⁻²¹.

Traditional Chinese Medicine adopts a holistic view of health, understanding it as a dynamic balance between the body's biological systems. Any disturbance in this balance can trigger a cascade of negative effects, affecting health as a whole ²². In the West, researchers are dedicated to unravelling the complexity of the philosophical and theoretical principles that underpin Traditional Chinese Medicine, seeking to understand its unique approach to health and well-being ²³⁻²⁷.

Despite its historical roots, Traditional Chinese Medicine has evolved and found a relevant place in contemporary medicine. Many professionals in the field, researchers, and organisations argue that TCM fits into the concept of "integrative medicine," offering a valuable complementary approach to conventional Western medicine methods ²⁸⁻³⁴.

Qigong, a millennial technique of Traditional Chinese Medicine, combines breathing exercises, static or dynamic movements, and meditative practices, aiming to achieve specific therapeutic benefits ³⁵. This practice can be considered an applied psychophysiological feedback technique, where the practitioner learns to regulate bodily functions and achieve homeostasis ³⁵. A European model of Traditional Chinese Medicine also recognises *Qigong* as a vegetative biofeedback technique, with diverse applications in health promotion ^{26,36-41}. Relevant to this study, the regular practice of therapeutic *Qigong* has been associated with cognitive and behavioural improvements ^{26,42-47}.

The objective of this study is to analyse the scientific evidence regarding *Qigong*'s effects on the cognitive and motor decline associated with Alzheimer's and Parkinson's diseases, as well as to explore the possibly associated mechanisms.

2. Dementia in Traditional Chinese Medicine

According to Li *et al.* ⁴⁸, ancient medical scriptures of Traditional Chinese Medicine already described symptoms similar to dementia, although the theoretical approach was completely distinct from Western medicine. The first records of cognitive decline in China date back about 2000 years. In Table 1, the specific imbalances attributed to dementia can be observed.

Table 1. TCM's dementia imbalances and consequences.

Imbalances	Consequences
Cerebral Dystrophy	Weakening or deterioration of brain functions.
Spleen-Kidney Weakness	Energetic imbalance that affects vitality and cognitive function.
<i>Xue</i> Stasis	Stagnation of blood flow, impairing tissue nourishment.
Phlegm Stagnation	Accumulation of bodily fluids that obscures the mind.

It is interesting to note that ancient Chinese doctors recognised that dementia manifested through a range of symptoms that went beyond cognitive decline, also including psychiatric disorders and sleep problems. The word "dementia" dates back to the legend

of the doctor Hua Tuo, at the end of the Eastern Han Dynasty. Also, the *Jingyue Quanshu*⁴⁹ contains a passage related to "manic-depressive syndrome and dementia" and states that stagnation, fear, fright, and excessive alarm are prominent causes of dementia.

Specifically, in Traditional Chinese Medicine, Alzheimer's Disease falls into the categories of "dementia", "apathy disease", and "forgetfulness", and patients exhibit "language errors", "amnesia", "idiocy", and "retarded thinking"⁵⁰. Also, Ma *et al.*⁵¹ state that the clinical symptoms of Alzheimer's Disease were described in the *Huangdi Neijing*, the oldest existing medical text in China, and it describes dementia in terms of "language errors" and "weak memory".

Traditional Chinese Medicine has a unique view on the pathogenesis, diagnosis, and treatment of Alzheimer's Disease, believing that a variety of internal factors can lead to cognitive dysfunction, including deficiencies in Kidney essence, *Qi*, and *Xue*. Thus, in Traditional Chinese Medicine, approaches to replenish *Qi*, detoxify, promote circulation, and remove *Xue* stasis are often used to treat Alzheimer's Disease in clinical practice⁵².

Furthermore, Liu *et al.*⁵³ state that, based on the characteristics of the condition's pathogenesis, which include "Kidney deficiency with medulla depletion as the root cause, accumulation of turbid phlegm as symptoms, disorder of the five visceral organs, and dysfunction of the cerebral medulla", ancient doctors employed various effective therapeutic approaches. Table 2 presents these approaches according to the author.

Table 2. TCM's Alzheimer's Disease treatments and objectives according to Liu *et al.*⁵³.

Treatment	Objective
Tonify the Kidney (<i>Shen</i>) and replenish the medulla (<i>Sui</i>).	Strengthen the Kidney and nourish the bone marrow.
Strengthen the Spleen (<i>Pi</i>) and benefit the <i>Qi</i> .	Improve regulatory capacity and vital energy.
Eliminate Phlegm (<i>Tan</i>) for resuscitation.	To remove the accumulation of bodily fluids and restore mental clarity.
Promote <i>Xue</i> circulation and invigorate <i>Qi</i> .	Improve blood flow and vital energy.

Regarding Parkinson's disease, in Traditional Chinese Medicine, it is associated with concepts such as *Chan Zheng* (tremors), *Chan Zhen* (agitation), and *Dong Feng* (shaking wind)⁵⁴.

In the classics of Traditional Chinese Medicine, Parkinson's Disease is described through symptomatic terms such as *Diao*, *Diao Xuan*, and *Qiang Zhi*. Ancient texts like the *Huang Di Nei Jing*⁵⁵ detail tremors, rigidity, and gait disturbances, while the *Su Wen Zhi Zhen Yao Da Lun*⁵⁶ links these to imbalances of Wind, Liver, and Kidney. Descriptions in the *Su Wen Mai Yao Jing Wei Lun*⁵⁶ link head tilting, postural changes, and gait problems to the exhaustion of organs and tissues, mirroring the symptoms of Parkinson's Disease. The *Zhu Bing Yuan Hou Lun Feng Si Zhi Ju Luan Bu De Qu Shen Hou*⁵⁷ attributes limb spasms to a deficiency of the liver channel, and the *Chi Shui Xuan Zhu*⁵⁸ identifies tremors in the hands and feet as "*Chan Zhen*", a key descriptor of Parkinson's Disease. Ren *et al.*⁵⁹ further connect "*Chan Zhen*", "*Zhen Zhuo*", and "*Tou Yao*" to Parkinson's Disease. In 1991, the Chinese Geriatric Society standardised the Traditional Chinese Medicine term for Parkinson's Disease as "geriatric tremor," solidifying its classification⁶⁰.

In their study, Hongzhi *et al.*⁵⁴ analysed disease patterns according to the principles of Traditional Chinese Medicine. In this study, through literature analysis and the application of statistical methods such as frequency and cluster analysis, they sought to identify the most prevalent Parkinson's Disease symptom patterns over the last 30 years. The main objective was to deepen the understanding of the fundamental and most common patterns of this condition, as they manifest in clinical practice. The results revealed six predominant symptom patterns, which together represent 66.06% of the total observed frequency, with cluster analysis highlighting four main patterns (Table 3).

Table 3. TCM's predominant symptoms and main patterns of Parkinson's disease according to Hongzhi *et al.* ⁵⁴.

Predominant Symptom Patterns	Main Patterns
Liver and Kidney Deficiency	
<i>Qi</i> and <i>Xue</i> Deficiency	Heat due to Phlegm and Shaking Wind
Phlegm Heat and Shaking Wind	Liver and Kidney <i>Yin</i> Deficiency
<i>Xue</i> Stasis and Shaking Wind	<i>Xue</i> Stasis and Shaking Wind
<i>Qi</i> Stagnation and <i>Xue</i> Stasis	<i>Qi</i> and <i>Xue</i> Deficiency
<i>Yin</i> and <i>Yang</i> Deficiency	

The comparison between the results of the frequency analysis and the cluster analysis revealed a significant concordance in the identification of the following patterns (Table 4).

Table 4. Basic Symptom Patterns of Parkinson's Disease according to Hongzhi *et al.* ⁵⁴.

Basic Symptom Patterns
Liver and Kidney <i>Yin</i> Deficiency
<i>Qi</i> and Blood Deficiency
Heat Due to Phlegm and Shaking Wind
<i>Xue</i> Stasis and Shaking Wind

Based on this concordance, the study concluded that these four patterns represent the basic symptom patterns of Parkinson's Disease, providing a solid basis for understanding and treating this condition in clinical practice.

3. Qigong for dementia

Although Mild Cognitive Impairment does not imply the presence or development of dementia, it can be a precursor. In this context, it is important to consider the scientific evidence that addresses this issue, as specific studies on dementia are scarce. To understand if *Qigong* (*Ba Duan Jin* sequence) has positive effects on maintaining cognitive abilities in the elderly at risk of cognitive decline, Jin *et al.* ⁶¹ developed a randomised controlled trial. Compared to stretching exercises, the 1-year program showed that participants in the *Qigong* group had a lower risk of cognitive decline progression. The results of statistical tests revealed that the values of the *Qigong* group were superior in terms of general cognitive ability, memory, visuospatial/constructive ability, and language. The values were only equivalent for attention levels. Thus, it is suggested that one year of *Qigong* practice may be superior to stretching exercise not only in preventing the progression of cognitive decline but also in improving various cognitive functions in the elderly at risk of cognitive decline.

Also using the *Qigong Ba Duan Jin* sequence, this time over 6 months in individuals with mild cognitive deficit, Liu *et al.* ⁶² sought to understand how this technique might act more systemically. Compared to a control group without intervention, participants in the *Qigong* group showed general improvements in cognitive function, namely in the areas of visual space and executive function, abstract memory, and delayed memory. However, the authors observed improvements in biochemical markers that may be related to the described improvements: the levels of total cholesterol, IL-6 (interleukin-6, an inflammatory marker) and MDA (malondialdehyde, an oxidative stress marker) decreased significantly, indicating an improvement in metabolic health and a reduction in oxidative stress and inflammation. Also, the levels of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL, the "good cholesterol"), Ach (acetylcholine, a neurotransmitter important for cognitive function), and SOD (superoxide dismutase, an antioxidant enzyme) increased significantly, suggesting improvements in cardiovascular health, neurotransmitter function and antioxidant protection. It is then suggested that *Qigong* may improve cognitive function, as well as reduce blood fat, oxidation, and inflammation levels in patients with mild cognitive deficit, and possibly prevent the development of diseases like Alzheimer's disease.

To better understand how these techniques act at the central level, Tao *et al.*⁶³ investigated how *Qigong* (*Ba Duan Jin*) and Taichi can modulate mental control function and resting-state functional connectivity (rsFC) of the cognitive control network in the elderly. In a 12-week intervention, the researchers found that, compared to a control, both *Qigong* and Taichi showed significant improvements in mental control function. Specifically, *Qigong* showed a significant decrease in rsFC between the DLPFC and the left putamen and insula. These results imply that *Qigong* is able to promote more efficient communication between areas crucial for cognitive control, motor control, and emotional regulation.

Exploring the above findings further, Tao *et al.*⁶⁴ confirmed the positive effects of *Qigong* (*Ba Duan Jin*) on cognitive function in a 24-week intervention. Regarding the results of magnetic resonance imaging, the analysis of the amplitude of low-frequency fluctuations (ALFF) showed that *Qigong* had significantly decreased values in the right hippocampus compared to the brisk walking group and increased ALFF values in the bilateral anterior cingulate cortex (ACC) compared to the control group. There was an increase in grey matter volume in these areas in the respective comparisons. Additionally, there was an increase in resting-state functional connectivity between the hippocampus and the right angular gyrus compared to the control group. The observed changes suggest that *Qigong* can have a positive impact on brain health, promoting structural and functional changes that contribute to the improvement of cognitive function in the elderly with mild cognitive impairment.

Also, Xia *et al.*⁶⁵ analysed through whole-brain functional magnetic resonance imaging and assessment of attention capacities, including selective, divided, and sustained attention, and processing speed, at the beginning and after 24 weeks of intervention. The results showed that *Qigong* (*Ba Duan Jin*) significantly increased the selective attention of patients with Mild Cognitive Impairment, and the Dorsal Attention Network (DAN) of the *Ba Duan Jin* exercise group exhibited decreased functional connectivity in the regions of the right rolandic operculum (ROL.R), right middle temporal gyrus (MTG.R), right inferior parietal supramarginal gyrus, angular gyri (IPL.R), right precuneus (PCUN.R) and right fusiform gyrus (FFG.R) compared to the other two control groups. They thus suggested that *Ba Duan Jin* can be a potentially beneficial intervention for improving attention in the elderly with Mild Cognitive impairment, modulating brain activity in areas crucial for attention control.

Regarding sleep in the elderly with cognitive impairment, the study by Chan *et al.*⁶⁶ showed that after 6 months, *Qigong* can improve sleep quality and quality of life compared to a control group.

Regarding Parkinson's disease, Moon *et al.*⁶⁷ developed a randomised controlled trial to understand the extent to which *Qigong* can help with the non-motor symptoms of the disease. They found that after 12 weeks of intervention, *Qigong* has significant effects on sleep quality, confirming the results previously achieved by the research team^{68,69}. In addition, the authors observed a reduction in TNF- α levels (elevated in Parkinson's patients and associated with disease progression), proposing that the improvement in sleep quality may be associated with changes in the inflammatory state and the immune system in general⁶⁹. In another controlled study lasting 12 months⁷⁰, the authors observed that *Qigong* caused a stabilising effect on motor performance and various non-motor symptoms such as constipation, pain levels, and sleep quality. Xiao *et al.*⁷¹ corroborate the previous results by observing that a 6-month *Qigong* intervention improved gait performance, functional mobility, and sleep quality in elderly people with Parkinson's Disease. Also, the study by Loftus⁷² demonstrated that the influence of *Qigong* on postural stability and rapid postural reflexes was positive. These improvements were verified through statistically significant changes in balance scores and a decrease in the number of falls.

4. Final remarks

The studies reported in this work allow us to suggest that *Qigong* is effective in preventing the progression of Mild Cognitive impairment and in improving various cognitive functions, including memory, visuospatial ability, and language. The benefits outweigh other types of physical exercise and non-intervention, which indicates a specific impact of *Qigong* on cognitive health. Some biochemical mechanisms appear to be associated with this positive action of *Qigong*, with a reduction in inflammatory and oxidative stress markers, and an improvement in metabolic and cardiovascular health. These changes may contribute to brain protection and the prevention of neurodegenerative diseases. Also, changes in brain activity and morphology seem to show how *Qigong* works. In these studies, *Qigong* was able to modulate brain activity by promoting more efficient communication between areas crucial for cognitive, motor, and emotional control, and attention, in addition to an increase in grey matter in specific areas. In addition to these benefits, *Qigong* increases selective attention, sleep quality, and quality of life. Regarding Parkinson's disease, *Qigong* seems to stabilise motor performance, improve gait, functional mobility, and postural stability, associated with a reduction in the number of falls and indicating a significant impact on the quality of life of patients. In addition, *Qigong* improves sleep quality and reduces the levels of inflammatory markers in Parkinson's patients, suggesting a positive impact on the immune system and the progression of the disease.

4.1. Limitations

The greatest limitation observed in this research is due to the small number of studies found on the topic. Due to this crucial limitation, a large portion of the included studies focus on the topic of cognitive decline, which, by itself, does not imply the development of Dementia. Also, the *Qigong* techniques studied have focused mainly on the *Ba Duan Jin* sequence.

4.2. Suggestions for future studies

According to the previous point, it is essential to conduct randomised and controlled clinical trials with participants diagnosed with different types of dementia (for example, Alzheimer's). It may also involve conducting longitudinal studies to monitor the effects of *Qigong* over several years. It will also be interesting to investigate whether the combination of *Qigong* with other therapies can produce synergistic effects. Finally, it is important to explore the existing differences between the various forms of *Qigong* and their application in different types of dementia.

5. Conclusions

Scientific evidence supports *Qigong* as a promising intervention for cognitive and neurological health. The benefits range from the prevention of cognitive decline to the improvement of Parkinson's disease symptoms. The modulation of brain activity, biochemical effects, and improvement of motor function contribute to the positive results of *Qigong*. Thus, *Qigong* emerges as a valuable mind-body practice to promote brain health and improve the quality of life in the elderly and patients with neurological conditions. More specific studies are needed.

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